

AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH OF NEEDS ASSESSMENT FOR FDP IN ENGINEERING INSTITUTIONS OF DELHI NCR

Shadma Parveen

Associate Professor Alfalah University
Faridabad, Haryana, India

Dr Daleep Paremoo

Professor Sharda University Greater
Noida, U.P. India

Abstract

Background: Faculty Development Training (FDT) is the stepping stone for the quality enhancement in Engineering and Technical Education. However, all the FDT are not according to the participant's needs and expectations because of dearth of information. Various reputed Engineering Institutions in Delhi and NCR, carried out an innovative approach to identify and prioritize faculty needs in order to plan future activities.

Methods: Investigator designed a questionnaire, based on Linkert 3 point scale, pilot-tested and administered to all faculty members (N=200). The respondents rated their perceived performance and their self-rated performance on each eleven competencies (subdivided into 74 sub-competencies), described in the literature. The ratings of perceived performance - high/moderate and self-rated performance average/poor were summed up to determine priority rankings for providing the continuous training and education to all Engineering Faculty. The respondents' rating of various continuing education activities, their willingness to participate and commit time and their suggestions and recommendations for strengthening Faculty Development Programmes (FDP) were also recorded and analyzed.

Results: All the eleven competencies were perceived as 'significant' by the respondents. They felt confident in teaching in large and small groups, developing attitude, interpersonal skill and decision making ability. The competencies prioritized as "gaps", identified how to improve the learning resources, plan curriculum, evaluate course content and conduct research work. The prioritized activities were to design specialized courses, organize orientation workshops for the newly appointed faculty and their training to improve their research skills. This implied a multiphase approach to Faculty Development Programme. A majority (62.4%) were willing to devote 2-3 hours per week to FDP. Respondents also suggested some measures to the Engineering Education Institution to improve their academicians' quality.

Conclusion: Researcher introduced and suggested a participatory approach to need assessment by identifying the gaps between "perceived performance" and "self-rated performance", as criteria for determining priorities. Findings also suggested the need for adopting a comprehensive approach to faculty development training in which both departmental and institutional initiatives are required. Findings are applicable to the Engineering Institutions of Delhi & NCR context but the methodology can be equally applied to any higher Education Institution of any state in India even around the Globe possibly.

Keywords: Need Assessment, Faculty Development Programmes (FDP), Engineering Education, Continuing Technical Education (CTE), Engineering Faculty Development Unit (EFDU) and Teaching Competency.

INTRODUCTION

Faculty development programs (FDP) has assumed utmost importance in meeting the diverse roles and responsibilities of an Engineering Educator as counselor, educator, administrator, leader, mentor, consultant, guide, evaluator, editor, researcher, organizer and coordinator of various academic and non academic programmes, member of various committees and societies in educational environment. Faculty Development programmes and

training needs to prepare the staff for performing their current role efficiently and effectively, making them perfect for their future role. Better teaching and research competencies will help the academic staff to grow in educational learning and development. The main driving forces for FDP are public accountability and the changing nature of Technical Education delivery and the need to sustain personal academic vitality. Stoll and Fink claims that nothing in Educational system probably has more impact on students in terms of knowledge and skill development, self-confidence or classroom behaviour than the personal and professional growth of their teachers. So continuous improvement in teacher competency, learning and development should be the part of institutional development activities. A recent World Bank paper on staff development recommends “a high quality and well motivated teaching staff and a supportive professional culture are essential in building excellence” (World Bank, 1994). So the competency improvement of Engineering Teacher is central to the quality of higher education in this era of knowledge society. According to Geraldo & Acuña (2005), the word “competence” drives from Latin word “competere” which represents aptitude, attitude, attributes, expertise, experiences and other competence specific characteristics required for effective performance at work place. McClelland (2006) was the first who proposed the idea of competence in various Human Resource Development Journals; demonstrated the relationship between excellent performer and their competence. Competence basically represents “what people can do.” In contrast, competency is “how they do it”. Competencies are important, as they help to communicate what an individual stands for or what the expectation is (Ernest, 1989). In order to achieve the optimum performance at work place, it is foremost required to identify the need for both hard (technical) as well as soft (general) competencies needed for Engineering Faculty and how they can be developed through training and development programmes. A great volume of literature on faculty development programs has been accumulated over past few decades with useful lessons. It has been reflected that FDP should be matched to the needs and expectations of individual students, teachers and the department as a whole. A systematic approach in FDT planning, implementation and evaluation was suggested by the various researchers and scholars from last few decades. FDT should contribute to self-directed lifelong learning, participatory educational approaches and update both the personal as well as professional competencies of Engineering Faculty. Ng, Chan and Wong (2006) categorised main competency into three levels, based on Engineering Competency Development (ECD)’s framework, (2006) as basic, intermediate and advanced competencies. Plonka, Hillman, Clarke, and Taraman (1994) explored the four core Engineering competencies as follows: (1) Discover yourself and work with others, (2) design, build and run high value-added manufacturing systems, (3) solve unstructured problems and (4) lead change. Bonjour, Hlaioittinun and Dulmet (2007), identified the difference between positive gap and negative gap, can be used to identify the level of competency.

Barr, Robert and John, (1995) emphasized the transition of teaching to learning process for Undergraduate Engineers. Braskamp and Larry A., (2000) developed a holistic approach to assess faculty. Shulman, Lee S., (2002) explained a table of learning to make difference in the development of teaching competency. John and Cullen, (2003) highlighted on Quality in Higher Education from monitoring management through the introduction of balance scorecard. Of these, the initial step of needs assessment is perhaps most crucial because it helps all teachers to realize their fullest potential and enables the program organizers to optimize and prioritize their activities. Engineering Colleges in Delhi NCR has witnessed a rapid increase in the enrolment of students (at least 20 fold increases in two decades), leading to a shortage of quality faculty around the Nation. Many reputed Engineering Colleges and institutions have established Engineering Faculty Development Unit (EFDU) to organize and implement faculty development activities in their respective institutions. The Indian govt has established 4 TTTI (Technical Teacher Training Institute) to train the technical teachers with the objective of enhancing faculty competencies in teaching, assessment and educational research. Most of the Private Engineering Institutions follow the conventional curriculum, operated by AICTE without many changes in a decade and expatriates of diverse backgrounds. A logical step for those directing the EFDU was therefore to conduct a needs assessment for FDP to inform their teachers in planning their future activities. The researcher principle objectives were to use a participatory process to prioritize the competencies on which to focus and the functional activities to be undertaken by the all EFDU. In the developmental efforts, the researcher also wanted to estimate the willingness of faculty to participate and the time they could devote, so the researcher could target a realistic set of activities. Finally, researcher sought to elicit suggestions from the Engineering faculty as the ways to strengthen

FDP initiatives. Previously published faculty needs assessment efforts of EFDU have employed a variety of tools and techniques including questionnaires, Likert scales, focus group interviews, interview schedules and Delphi techniques, generally to assess continuing Engineering Education (CEE) needs in various settings. Only few studies have captured the differences between perceptions of ‘what an ideal CEE should be’ and ‘what is actually practiced’. There were two studies particularly relevant to this study. One attempted to assess the difference between participants’ ‘current capability and potential’ with the ‘ideal one’ in their various roles and responsibilities and the other study depicts the differences between ‘perceived performance’ and ‘self-rated performance’ as the basis for prioritizing FDP needs. Another important initiative in this field is the effort of Hesketh et al., dealt with twelve competencies expected from higher education academicians. This study considers these twelve competencies as the basis for FDP needs assessment in the private Engineering Institution and also considers the view that FDP should be prioritized on the basis of difference (gap) between expected competencies and actual performance of faculty. The greater the gap between expected and actual performance, the greater the need for these areas to be stressed in FDP efforts.

Researcher drafted a semi-structured, partly open-ended and partly closed-ended questionnaire. Central in the questionnaire was a three point Likert scale in which respondents were asked to rate the perceived performance (high, moderate, low) and their current performance (good, average, poor) on each of eleven competencies derived from the work of Hesketh et al. Other important issues addressed in the questionnaire were the perceived functional activities and services provided by the EFDU. The questions were asked to rate the activities in terms of relevance and usefulness to bolstering their performance. These items were derived from the literature and the experience of the researcher. Questions were also asked from the faculty to indicate their willingness to participate in FDP and the amount of time, they could devote to this FDP. Open ended questions were asked to elicit comments and suggestions from the respondents for strengthening FDP. A questionnaire was drafted and reviewed by the researcher for its content validity, then pilot-tested with 12 faculty member volunteers to assess the validity of scale in terms of time required for completion, language and user-friendliness. The questionnaire consists of 12 broad competencies and one is eliminated, not considered very important after pilot survey. The questionnaire was modified and finalized based on feedback of respondents of pilot study. It was administered through the HOD of all the departments to the Engineering faculty members (n=200) of 10 private Engineering Institutions of Delhi NCR. The names of Institutions were remained confidential as promised by the respondents. Respondents were reassured that responses would remain strictly confidential and Completion was voluntary.

Analysis:

The analysis of numerical data was carried out using Excel sheet. The ratings made by the participants with respect of the ‘perceived performance’ versus ‘self-rated performance’ for each of the eleven competencies were tabulated in the form of a 3 x 3 contingency table, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The table highlighted the ratings of the participants on “Perceived performance” and “Self-rated Performance” for a given competency is combined to calculate a priority score.

Perceived Performance	Self-Rated Performance			
	Poor	Average	Good	Total
High	0	12	72	84
Moderate	0	4	9	13
Low	0	0	0	0
Total	0	16	81	97

Perceived performance is high as 84 and self-rated performance is good as 81. The priority score is calculated as the sum of rating in respect of four cells that is perceived performance (high/moderate) and self-rated performance (poor/average) ; i.e. = 16. The researcher counted the number of responses for perceived performance as well as self-rated performance for each of the eleven competencies. For calculating the priority scores, the researcher summed the four cells pertaining to perceived performance (High/Average) and self rated Performance (Poor/Moderate). The sum represents the gap between perceived performance and self rated performance, or the 'training deficit'. The priorities of competencies were ranked according to the deficit scores. For prioritizing the activities expected from the EFDU, researcher relied on response counts and ranked them accordingly. Furthermore, the researcher counted the number of educators who were willing to participate as teachers or resource persons and calculated the mean time and range to quantify this information.

The qualitative analysis of the open-ended comments, recommendations and suggestions for strengthening FDP was initially undertaken by the researcher who listed all comments, identified general competencies and sub-competencies and then grouped all comments within them. Furthermore the Questionnaire was then checked independently by the researcher as a verification of these eleven competencies and the proper grouping of all the seventy two sub competencies under these eleven competencies through analysis. Furthermore all the comments and suggestions were recorded under the suitable competency themes. The competency theme assignment differences were resolved through proper discussion.

Results:

Participants' Profile

A total of 110 questionnaires were returned out of 200, yielding a response rate of 55%. Table 2 describes the response rate by gender, faculty designation and by Engineering versus Applied Sciences department appointment. All the different departments of Undergraduate Engineering courses were represented among respondents except English. Sixty seven (60.9%) faculty members had more than 12 years of experience. Response rates were not different among faculty ranks and between various Core Engineering and Applied Sciences Department. However, the response rate was higher in males versus females because male faculty are generally more in numbers in Technical Education as compare to female. It has also been realised that male are more interested in research and innovative activities than female counterpart.

Table 2: Survey of participants and responses rate by gender, faculty rank, and Engineering versus Applied Sciences Department appointment

Demographical Information	Total Faculty Selected (N=200)	Respondents (N=110)	P-value
Gender:			
Male	118 (59%)	82(69.5%)	0.001**
Female	82 (41%)	28 (34.14%)	
Rank:			
Professor	42 (21%)	28 (66.7%)	0.153
Associate Professor	64 (32%)	30(46.87%)	
Assistant Professor	94 (47%)	52(55.31%)	
Department:			
Core Engineering	140 (70%)	76(54.28%)	0.566
Applied science	60 (30%)	32(53.3%)	

** P-value is very significant at .01-.009 significant levels. There is a significant difference between male and female response rate because male are more interested in research activities and ready to devote the time as various earlier studies have already demonstrated.

Table 3: Respondents' rating of perceived performance, self-rated performance, priority scores and priority ranking on eleven engineering teaching competencies

S/n o.	Competencies	Perceived performance 1	Self-rated Performance 2	Priority (Deficit) scores 3	Priority Ranking 4
1	Instructing in the group	84	81	16	11
2	Teaching the core Engineering concepts	85	70	26	10
3	Facilitating learning	73	60	35	5
4	preparing lesson plan and course file	74	46	52	2
5	Updating learning materials and resources	72	42	54	1
6	Problem solving ability	81	61	32	8
7	Evaluating course contents and undertaking research	72	47	49	3
8	Developing understanding of educational principles and techniques	75	55	37	4
9	Attitudes, attributes and ethical values	86	80	16	11
10	Ability to take Quick and correct decision making	81	74	23	10
11	Communication and administrative skills	73	61	35	5

Prioritization of Competencies

As the Table 3 shows the respondents' rating of perceived performance and their self-rated performance, the priority scores and the ranking of priorities derived for all the eleven competencies independently. All the eleven competencies were observed as significant by the faculty, as mentioned by their ratings which ranged between 72 and 86. However, self-rated performance received highest ranking on instructing in the group (81), attitudes, attributes and ethical values (80), ability to take quick and correct decision making (74), The faculty felt least confident in developing learning materials and resources (42), preparing lesson plan and course file (46) and evaluating course contents and undertaking research (47). The priority scores derived from the sum of ratings of four cells – perceived performance high/average and self-rated performance poor/average are shown in the Table 3, developing learning materials and resources (54) received highest priority followed by preparing lesson plan and course file (52) and evaluating course contents and undertaking research (49). Ability to take quick and correct decision (23) attitudes attributes and ethical values (16) and instructing in group (16) received least priority.

Table 5: Ranking of Suggested Activities by respondents for Faculty Development programme:

Ranking	Suggested Activity	Total Rating	percentage
1	Pedagogy Training	105	95.4
2	Orientation Training for newly appointed Faculty	101	91.8
3	Training in undertaking research and development activities	100	90.9
4	Specialized courses (Setting question paper and evaluation)	98	89.1
5	Training in teaching in a simulated class room	85	77.3
6	Basic short term training for specialized courses.	82	74.5
7	Counselling the teachers when required	78	70.9
8	Providing assistance in undertaking educational projects	76	69.1
9	Sponsoring faculty to pursue higher education	72	65.4

Note 1. Some more activities suggested are: Workshops in Research Methodology, Industrial Research and Publication, Engineering Ethics, Academic Leadership, Participative Teaching, Oral Examination, Facilitating Changes, Developing Higher Cognitive and Psychomotor Skills, Mentorship, Class Room Management and Understanding Student Psychology.

Faculty Training and Development Need Assessment Survey (2014), Engineering Institutions, Delhi NCR:

Willingness to Participate in the FDP Activities:

Maximum number of participants (61.4%) expressed their willingness to participate in the activities of EFDU and ability to spend an average of 2-3 hours per week for this purpose. Those faculty members who are willing to join as resource persons (33.6%) indicated that they can spare 2.5 hours per week. Only five percent indicated that they have no time for FDP.

Comments and Recommendations for Strengthening FDP:

The comments and **recommendations** mentioned by the respondents were recorded within two categories: Initiatives to be taken by the Engineering Institutions and those to be followed by the EFDU (Table 5). The initiatives expected at the Institutional level were to take a strategic decision for participation in FDP activities to be compulsory for faculty, strengthen FDP infrastructure and facilities and provision for incentives and recognition. The initiatives taken by EFDU were assumed more powerful and responsibilities to monitor content delivery, prepare an academic calendar of activities, distribute learning materials and resources and emphasis on practical aspects of FDP were consider significant.

Table 5: Comments and Recommendations made by the respondents for strengthening the FDP:

Category	Comments / Recommendations
Management Initiatives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Participation in FDP should be compulsory for all Engineering Faculty. 2. FDP participation should start even before the appointment as a faculty; Talented and potential faculty members should be trained in Teaching Technology. 3. Engineering teachers should be provided the recognition and incentives for their contribution to teaching and learning. "Best Teacher" awards should be given to the deserving teachers, protected time for FDP, conferences, seminars and symposium etc. for updating their teacher's knowledge. 4. The management must focus the issues of Continuous Improvements especially in setting the paper and conducting exams and also in facilities and resources' for the faculty to be more productively engaged in research/publication. 5. The management must also address the other issues like improving the quality of labs, laboratories and equipments. The more emphasis should be on practical exposure rather than theory. 6. Develop more and more collaboration between diverse teachers in terms of sex, age, cast, region and religion.
Departmental Initiatives by EFDU	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>EFDU should be authorised the power</i> to standardize the Curriculum of FDP and review of course content. They should monitor and evaluate all the steps taken by the departments to improve standard. 2. Organize the FDP on a <i>continual basis</i> by announcing the activities in the <i>academic calendar</i> so that all teachers can participate in turn, without jeopardizing their other departmental duties and responsibilities. 3. <i>Learning materials and resources</i> should be provided in the form of notes booklet, CD and hand-outs etc. 4. Arrange guest lectures and invite at least two-three <i>international guest speakers</i> twice or thrice a year. 5. The <i>focus should be on Industrial and practical exposures</i> rather than theoretical aspects. 6. Training in Engineering Educational Research should be part and parcel of FDP. 7. The duration of workshops should not be longer than 8 hours. 8. Faculty development programs should encourage students' involvement, e.g. in obtaining feedback on teaching and assessment.

Discussion:

This study depicts a participatory approach to all Engineering Institutions' for needs assessment in which the maximum faculty is involved in identifying FDP needs and priorities. Researcher has prepared his own framework from earlier studies and utilised a method of arriving at the priority areas based on the gap between the competencies that faculty perceive as most important for their roles and how they rate their own performance on these competencies. The needs identified and prioritized by the respondents can be expressed on the basis of their geographical information, experiences and local context. The respondents in the study are mostly senior Engineering and Applied Science Faculty with more than 12 years of experience. It is natural for them to think that their teaching Competency, should be satisfactory but they need to update their knowledge in developing learning materials and resources, planning curriculum, lesson and conducting research and development activities in handling new technologies like e-learning and sustaining academic vitality and leadership towards the end of their career.

Decision-making received low priority by maximum of the predominantly expatriate faculty, who do not occupy many administrative responsibilities. Attitudes and ethical values are considered to be "self-learned behaviours", rather than "moulded" by FDP. Contrary to the researcher expectations, the competency in learner assessment was given average priority as reflected through series of workshops attended by faculty in this context conducted by the EFDU during the last three years.

The activities prioritized for FDP through identifying gaps between perceived performance and current performance should be accepted along with the faculty's suggestions for strengthening FDP initiatives. The respondents expect that the EFDU would tailor its activities for FDP according to different experiences. Accordingly, all newly appointed faculties are sensitized through an orientation program. Maximum faculty would attend basic instructional workshops; only few would opt for subject specific workshops to understand the concepts and principles of their specialised skills (hard skills), conduct research and development and assume academic leadership and vitality. This study has already depicted earlier as multi-phased or multi-tiered approach to FDP. Less emphasis was paid on providing consultation to the faculty on certain issues (e.g., how to improve group participation), training the faculty for undertaking educational projects and sponsoring interested faculty for higher education (e.g., M.Tech and PhD and other certificate courses).

A major improvement in the field of FDP is that FDT does not rest on the efforts of the few individuals who organize FDT but also depends upon organizational variables including the institution's infrastructure and facilities, overall academic leadership, incentives and also the recognition to the faculty for contributing to FDP. This is reported by respondents' suggestions for strengthening FDP and the operations of the EFDU as mentioning the FDP activities in academic calendar and providing the learning materials (a booklet to all trainees) and resources within the purview of EFDU. Moreover another important step to be taken for making the faculty participation a mandatory requirement as setting standardizing Questions papers, monitoring the quality of courses content and strengthening altogether institutional infrastructure.

A valuable contribution of the study is the data obtained on the willingness of the faculty to participate in FDP and the time they could devote as either a participant or a resource person to FDP, not mentioned in the earlier studies. The researcher plan to create a database of those educators, willing to join as participants or resource persons, could be engaged in scheduling future FDP.

The study involves some limitations. The data obtained through the questionnaire, especially the self rated performance by the respondents, is likely to involve certain desirability biasness. The educators may not correctly recognize the limitations of their competency as a teacher. Respondents are likely to over-report their willingness to devote time to FDP but their actual cooperation may be less than their promises. Moreover, what data researcher has collected is preliminary information. Further assessments are needed to validate the findings by incorporating other tools such as Delphi technique, focus group interviews, interview schedule and other suggestions and recommendations collected from faculty in open house discussion. Though the findings of the study are immediately applicable in the Engineering Education setting, the methodology might be replicable in any higher education setting in India as well as around the globe.

Conclusion:

The researcher undertook a participatory approach through this needs assessment survey which is easy, feasible and useful in Delhi and NCR Region context and may also be equally applicable in other regions. The researcher emphasised on identifying the gap between faculty's perceived performance and self-rated performance on eleven competencies, as criteria for prioritizing FDP. This study also collected the database for identifying participants who are willing to commit time to FDP as facilitators and learners. This study also focused the need for adopting a multi-phased approach in delivering faculty development training and tailored to faculty at each career stage and emphasized the roles of both EFDU and Engineering Institutions in strengthening FDP.

Authors: Ms Shadma Parveen currently working as an Associate Professor at the department of Management Studies of Alfalah University Faridabad Haryana. She has 14 years of experience (Industry and teaching). She has presented and published various National and International research papers and articles in journal and non academic media.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS: The author would like to impart sincere thank for the advice and support of Chancellor AFU Faridabad; Janab Jawad Ahmad Siddiqui, the Vice Chancellor of AFU Faridabad; Prof Dr. Anil Kumar and also Prof. Daleep Paremoo who have immensely supported to conduct this study. I am also very much thankful to Mr Khaleek Ahmad, HOD Civil Deptt. of AFU, who not only motivated but also contributed their precious time to complete this study

REFERENCES:

- [1] Ernest Joshua, (1989) Competency Based Curriculum Design for Technical Education –An Indian Experiment, Manila, Philippines: Colombo Plan Staff College for Technician Education, Proceedings of the International Conference on Technical Education.
- [2] Ernest Joshua, (1989) Competency Based Curriculum Design for Technical Education –An Indian Experiment, Manila, Philippines: Colombo Plan Staff College for Technician Education, Proceedings of the International Conference on Technical Education.
- [3] M. G. Fullan, (1991) “The New Meaning of Educational Change” London: Cassel Educational Publishers.
- [4] Spencer, L.M. and Spencer, S.M. (1993) Competence at Work: Models for Superior Performance, New York: John Wiley and Sons.
- [5] Menges, Robert J., & Associates (1999), *Faculty in new jobs*, San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- [6] Austin, Ann E. (2002), “Creating a bridge to the future: Preparing new faculty to face changing expectations in shifting context,” *The Review of Higher Education*, 26 (2), 119-144.
- [7] Chambers, Tony (2002), *Helping students find their place and purpose: Tony Chambers talks with Sharon Park, About Campus*, 20-24.
- [8] Stenmark, D. (2003) ‘Knowledge creation and the web: Factors indicating why some intranets succeed where others fail, *Knowledge and Process Management*, pp. 207-216.
- [9] Stenmark, D. and Lindgren R. (2006) ‘System Support for Knowledge Work: Bridging the Knowing-Doing Gap’. *International Journal of Knowledge Management*, pp.46-68.

- [10] Ryan, Katherine E. (Ed.). (2003) "Evaluating teaching in higher education: A vision for the future, *New Directions for Teaching and Learning*", Number 83, San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- [11] McClelland, M. (2003), Metadata standards for educational resources, *IEEE Computer*, 36, (11), 107-109.
- [12] Muzychenko, O. and Sae, J. (2004) Cross Cultural Professional Competence in Higher Education, *Journal of Management Systems*, Vol 16, No 4, pp. 1-20.
- [13] S. C. Anyamele, (2004), Institutional Management in Higher Education: A Study of Leadership Approaches to Quality Improvement in University Management, Nigerian and Finnish Cases, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Department of Education, University of Helsinki.
- [14] F.D. Le Deist and J. Winterton, (2005). "What is Competence?" *Human Resource Development International* journal 8, no.1, The authors have done extensive research on various competency models used in different countries and assessed performance into a useful typology.
- [15] Ranjan J, Tripathi P. (2007). "Decision Supporting System for the Competence Management", Proceedings of the First International Conference on Information System Technology and Management.
- [16] Ranjan J, Tripathi P. (2008). "Measuring Competencies using Expert System: Educational Perspective" *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*.
- [17] Hanna Pačaiová, (2008), "Quality and Competence Measurement" in 'On the way from integrated management systems to generic management systems', editor Petra Winzer, Shaker Verlag (in print).
- [18] Muzychenko O., Seet P. S. and Wells S. April. (2008), working in culturally diverse groups: How to enhance the learning experience of MBA students, Proceeding of the *International Conference on Educational Leadership in Cultural Diversity and Globalization*, Phuket, Thailand, 8-10.
- [19] Eva Vogt (2008), "The Competence Circle" in 'On the way from integrated management systems to generic management systems', editor Petra Winzer, Shaker Verlag (in print) Evaluation Sheet for Students and Teachers of the Department of Engineering, Chair of Product Safety and Quality Engineering, unpublished
- [20] R.K shahu (2009) Competencies Mapping, Excel books publishers New Delhi.
- [21] B. Bloom et al, (1956) *Taxonomy of Educational Objectives: Handbook I, The cognitive domain* New York, David McKay & Co., Bloom's work has been utilized worldwide.
- [22] K.L Rawal, (14 Sep 2010), The Strategic Competencies Management in Indian Perspective, *Journal of Industrial Relation*.
- [23] Stephen, chukwnyenye, Anyamele, Managing professional competencies of teaching staff in the University; view of Finish University Leaders, *Academic Leadership, Live on line Journals*, Vol. 8 issue4.

**S. Parveen & D. Paremoo / An Innovative Approach of Needs Assessment for FDP in Engineering
Institutions of Delhi NCR**

[24] Mann KV. Not another survey! Using questionnaires effectively in needs assessment, *The Journal of Continuing Education in the Health Professions*, 1998; 18:142-149.

[25] Wallin DL, Smith CL. Professional development needs of full-time faculty in Technical Colleges, *Community College Journal of Research and Practice*, 2005; 29: 87-108.